

5GTopoNet: Real-Time Topology Discovery and Management on 5G Multi-Tenant Networks

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Abstract

The Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks leverage virtualisation and softwarisation to reduce both capital and operating expenditures whilst benefiting from network programmability and flexibility for various use cases. Meanwhile, virtualisation and softwarisation introduce unprecedented complexity to network infrastructure topologies, which poses substantial challenges to network topology management. This paper proposes a novel architecture to enable network administrators to achieve real-time network discovery and spatial representation of the software data path, containers, virtual machines, and geographically distributed edges to help network troubleshooting and management tasks. Another important innovation is the flexibility to support a significant number of business roles by means of a novel method to perform data model alignment between different business roles. The architecture has been designed, prototyped and validated, and experiment results have demonstrated promising scalability of the proposed solution.

Keywords: Mobile Edge Computing, 5G, Network Management, Network Topology, Network Inventory

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1. Introduction

Virtualisation and softwarisation are the cornerstone of the forthcoming Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks. The resultant 5G software data paths, combining virtual and physical networks, pose significant challenges in understanding the network topology of the novel virtualised and softwarised 5G network architectures for data centre administrators, telecommunication operators, and infrastructure providers for network management purposes. The challenges are exacerbated by 5G multi-tenancy, which enables multiple tenants such as network operators to share the same physical infrastructure, to reduce capital and operating costs significantly [1]. Multi-tenancy imposes the usage of overlay networks to perform resource and network isolation for each of the tenants over the same physical infrastructure. Such isolation requires the creation of new logical networks and virtual machines (VMs) per tenant, which in turn leads to a more complex network topology and thus more complicated troubleshooting of networking issues. Furthermore, the challenge is propagated to different geographical locations in 5G networks where multi-tenancy is extended to the edges of the network in the Mobile/Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) paradigm to facilitate localised processing and thus help meet ambitious 5G Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Moreover, there is a clear need to differentiate business roles associated to the multi-tenant infrastructure. This separation between Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP) and Infrastructure Service Consumer (ISC) is currently happening in various cases involving public cloud providers, telecommunication providers, digital service providers and other business roles. The separation of business roles entails the definition of the topological boundaries between the ISP physical network and the ISC virtual tenant networks. This has significant implications in terms of technical and legal responsibilities, since this business role separation can determine the physical and virtual scopes of the administrative domains. The complexity of the network topology is even greater when the infrastructure needs to deal with the mobility of user equipment between different access points, which is associated to 5G networks where

user mobility, multi-tenant isolation and virtualisation are key elements. The understanding of such complexity in network topology is a critical aspect for the successful adoption of these technologies and efficient network management. In operational 5G environments, services need to be delivered to a large number
35 of users, and network issues can rise from any of the physical and virtual network interfaces. Therefore, the complexity in 5G network topology has become prohibitively high for conventional network management platforms to handle, and existing network topology awareness tools are not capable of circumventing these challenges.

40 The main contribution of this paper is the design, implementation and validation of a highly innovative architecture to enable network administrators to obtain real-time network discovery and spatial representation of 5G network topology, thereby empowering them to handle the complexity of the 5G multi-tenant network infrastructure. The proposed architecture enables both physical
45 and virtual network topology representations and their interconnection. The main innovation is the proposed solution that addresses the following outstanding challenges:

1. The architecture should deal with the complexity associated to the software data path and the usage of virtualisation and containerisation.
- 50 2. The architecture should deal with the complexity associated to the geographical distribution of the architectural components in the novel 5G networks (edge and core networks).
3. The architecture should support both multi-tenancy and user mobility.
4. The architecture should be flexible enough to allow use cases with the ISP
55 and ISC business role separation.
5. The architecture should be flexible enough to allow the representation of the network topologies from different perspectives: ISP, ISC, and ISP and ISC (ISP + ISC), respectively.
6. The architecture should be able to identify and understand the topological
60 boundaries between ISP and ISC.

The proposed architecture has been designed, prototyped and integrated in a real multi-tenant 5G network, currently deployed in our premises. An intensive functional validation has been carried out to validate the innovations indicated above. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 analyses the state of the art in network topology architectures and software. Section 3 describes the proposed novel architecture, including details of each component in the architecture. Section 4 presents a sequence diagram to explain the design and behaviour of the architecture. Section 5 shows implementation details and challenges associated to the different software components prototyped. Section 6 presents empirical results about the validation and scalability of the proposed architecture. Finally, Section 7 provides conclusions and future work.

2. Related Work

Multi-tenant 5G networks pose several challenges that the current topology tools are unable to overcome to allow real-time spatial representation of the network. This section provides a comprehensive enumeration of these challenges, as listed in Table 1. Furthermore, Table 2 provides an overview analysis of the challenges introduced in Table 1 in the state of the art compared with the proposed architecture in this paper to allow a clear identification of our contribution. In the following, we provide a detailed review of these work.

Total Network Inventory [2] and AixBOMS [4] are examples of traditional network inventory management system for use in offices, companies, and small and large corporate networks. They provide tools for layout plans, rack management and visualisation, power management, reports and detailed technical device information. Sanby et al. [3] reported a Traceroute study carried out on African NRENs, demonstrating the joint use of different probing protocols to achieve a 65% reduction in the number of probe packets sent to discover the network topology. All these systems rely on OSI Layer 3 (L3) discovery mechanisms so that they simply do not show any device along the path and just connectivity between devices and at most IP network topologies.

ID	Description of Discovery Challenge
I	Physical Network Topologies (L1) between Devices
II	Logical Network Topologies (L2) between Computers
III	Virtual Machine Overlay Topologies
IV	Virtual Network Overlay Topologies
V	Container Machine Overlay Topologies
VI	Container Network Overlay Topologies
VII	Multi-tenant Information for III (see III)
VIII	Multi-tenant Information for IV (see IV)
IX	Geographical Distribution of Machines (Edge/Core)
X	Specialised Physical Devices (Software-Defined Radio Devices)
XI	LTE/5G UE Topologies
XII	LTE/5G UE Mobility across Radio Access Networks (Antennas)
XIII	Supported Business Role: ISP
XIV	Supported Business Role: ISC
XV	Supported Business Role: ISP + ISC
XVI	Alignment between ISP and ISC reported topologies
XVII	Integrated ISP / ISC Perspectives

Table 1: Challenges to achieve a real-time multi-tenant 5G network topology

90 nuGENTM3D Visualisation for IoT Networks [5] is a Visual Network Visualisation Management System (NMS) for physical networks. It simplifies the management and optimisation of networks via visualisation of the entire network and its dynamics in real-time. nuGENTM has cloud-based and on-premise versions, with real-time analytics. NuGEN claims to be suitable for discovering 95 virtual networks; however, the discovery methods supported do not indicate so. They are ping sweep, SSH, Telnet, DNS and SNMP and none of these methods allows discovering overlay networks, which are directly associated to virtual infrastructures.

Zhou and Ma [6] proposed an algorithm to discover physical layout topology structure of Ethernet networks with incomplete address forwarding table 100 information. Their algorithm can handle both Layer-2 switches with VLAN and Layer-3 switches. Analogously, Wang et al. [7] introduced a network topology discovery algorithm based on SNMP, which can discover the target topology completely and accurately through combining the topology discovery of the 105 network layer and link layer. They identify that there are many different manu-

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV	XV	XVI	XVII
Total Network Inventory[2]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
R. Sanby et al. [3]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
AixBOMS [4]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
nuGEN [5]	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Zhou and Ma [6]	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Wang et al. [7]	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Jiang et al. [8]	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Rojas et al. [9]	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
NMSaaS [10]	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Network Topology Mapper [11]	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Toufga et al. [12]	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
OpenDayLight [13]	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Skydive [14]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
MidoNet[15]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
5GTopoNet (Ours Contribution)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 2: Analysis of the state of the art with respect to our contribution against the challenges required to achieve real-time multi-tenant 5G network topologies

factures and various kinds of equipment in the network, and every manufacture has their own support on SNMP whilst the impact of the heterogeneity is left for future work. In addition, Jiang et al. [8] relied on SNMP to propose an effective topology algorithm that improves the efficiency and quality of the discovery process.

Rojas et al. [9] presented a Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol (TEDP), an alternative protocol to the Link-Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP), proving that shortest paths can be built simultaneously when the topology information is gathered, without extra messages compared with LLDP. They also analysed two alternative implementations for TEDP and give insights into some features that Software-Defined Networking (SDN) platforms should ideally provide for an efficient topology discovery service. They provide support for the discovery

of overlay networks. In the same direction, NMSaaS [10] is another network discovery software, which uses SNMP (V1, V2c, V3) (CDP protocol), WMI, ICMP, WMI, VMware and more to discover IT assets and creates dynamic maps based on Layer 2 and Layer 3 connections. It is noted that the integration with the hypervisor allows the discovery of the virtual assesses. SolarWinds provides the Network Topology Mapper software [11] that automatically discovers and delineates network topology and produces comprehensive, easy-to-view network diagrams. It supports multiple discovery methods, including SNMP v1-v3 (CDP and LLDP protocols), ICMP, WMI, CDP, VMware, Hyper-V, and more. It can provide reports on switch ports, VLANs, subnets, and inventory. It also directly addresses PCI compliance, FIPS 140-2, and others that require maintenance of an up-to-date network diagram. Toufga et al. [12] presented an effective topology discovery service for SDN-based hybrid vehicular networks. They demonstrate that the “defacto” OpenFlow-based topology discovery service is not adapted for Software-Defined Vehicular Networks and thus they propose some directions to follow in order to address the highlighted limits and to design an efficient topology discovery service more suited to vehicular networks.

OpenDayLight (ODL) [13] is a modular open platform for customising and automating network control, monitoring and discovery at scale. ODL provides control for multi-tenant isolation in cloud computing stacks such as OpenStack. Thus, it is aware of the multi-tenant overlay networks. Moreover, Skydive [14] and MidoNet [15] are advanced open-source real-time network topology tools able to discover physical and overlay networks of both virtual machines and containers with multi-tenant support.

However, none of the above solutions is able to provide support for the creation of 5G network topology where 5G users need to be discovered, and tracked while moving across antennas, where 5G VMs are migrating in a matter of seconds leading to the change of the network topology, and where specialised hardware such as radio equipment needs to be also discovered. Almost all the software analysed could be executed in either ISP or ISC, and they can

discover the corresponding topology for the respective business role. However,
 150 none of these systems is able to perfectly align the topologies reported from the
 different business roles together. This lack of alignment makes impossible use
 cases where both ISP and ISC are the same organisation, which is a typical
 scenario for 5G mobile operators. It also hampers providing network discovery
 as a service to ISCs and integrated ISP and ISC network topology view to ISPs
 155 for troubleshooting support to ISCs. All these open issues have been the main
 motivation of this research.

3. 5G Multi-tenant Infrastructure

Figure 1: Multi-tenant 5G Network Overview

This section describes the 5G multi-tenant network infrastructure managed
 by our proposed architecture. This infrastructure is illustrated in Fig. 1. Two
 160 different levels of network infrastructure are depicted to represent an illustrative
 example of a 5G multi-tenant network topology where the essential components
 of both physical and virtual overlay network infrastructures. The lower network
 is the Physical Network. Multiple 5G users gain access to this physical network
 by being connected to the Radio Access Network via different Distributed Units
 (DUs) using the 5G terminology [16]. Multiple DUs are then connected to a
 165 pool of Central Units (CUs) at the same Edge of the network using a Cloud-
 RAN deployment. An Edge is a Point of Presence (PoP) of the infrastructure
 located very close to the final users where computational processing can be
 allocated to achieve low-latency communications between the infrastructure and

170 users. Multiple Edges are connected to the Core Network where there is a set
of physical machines, usually located in the data centre premises. An Edge
has limited processing capabilities, whereas the Core has significantly higher
capabilities. The Core network has a data centre layout where there are several
compute machines (only one compute machine is shown for clarity). These
175 compute machines gain access to the Internet by mean of a network device. This
physical infrastructure runs a cloud stack that allows multi-tenant isolation of
the different physical resources through virtualisation. This cloud stack is able
to deal with physical machines that are geographically separated from the data
centre, such as the different Edges of the infrastructure.

180 Analogously, the upper level of Fig. 1 is the Virtual Network. It is com-
posed by a set of virtual machines, containers and/or name-spaces, depending
on the vitalisation technology employed. Henceforth all of them will be referred
indistinctly as VMs even though they are a mix of these technologies for brevity.
The logical components of the 5G network run inside of the physical machines
185 and each logical component belongs to a particular tenant of the network. As
shown in Fig. 1, switches join both physical and virtual networks. They are
software switches such as Linux Bridges or Open vSwitch [17], which allow the
enforcement of the tenant isolation between different VMs.

VMs are depicted in different colours to emphasize the ownership of them. It
190 is noted that there are VMs that are deployed on Edge physical machines and
others deployed in Core physical machines; it extends multi-tenancy support
to the edge of the network, creating a MEC infrastructure. In Fig. 1, there
are two different tenants sharing the same physical infrastructure. The tenant
network is represented as a conceptual “virtual hub”, which is just an illusion
195 for the perception of the ISC and allows communication among all the VMs
that belong to the same tenant. This architecture allows every tenant to share
the same physical infrastructure to have its own isolated network. Such “virtual
hub” is in reality implemented using overlay networks such as VXLAN and GRE
network encapsulation technologies.

200 Other architectural components in the 5G architecture include User Plane

Function (UPF) for access to the Internet, Access and Mobility Function (AMF) for User Equipment (UE) based authentication, authorisation and mobility management, Session Management Function (SMF) for session management and IP address allocation to UE, and so on (Kim et al. [16]). All these 5G components with the only exception of the DU are fully softwarised. In this work, we focus on the AMF and SMF components for handling user mobility and tracking a user throughout the network.

4. 5GTopoNet Architecture Overview

Figure 2: 5GTopoNet Architecture Overview

This section describes the 5GTopoNet architecture proposed to achieve the real-time topologies of 5G multi-tenant networks. This novel architecture is illustrated in Fig. 2. Each box represents a software component, and each circle represents a topic in a publication/subscription message bus architecture. These topics allow all the subscribed components (those with an arrow from the topic) to receive the message sent by the publishing component (those with an arrow to the topic). Some of these components are also depicted in Fig. 1 to show where they are deployed in the network. Those not shown are deployed in another physical machine for management purposes. The architecture comprises a set of software agents that are responsible for gathering the topological information, keeping it up-to-date and reporting the changes about such information to the “Topology” exchange topic. These agents are described as follows:

Resource Inventory Agent (RIA) is a component deployed inside each physical machine of the 5G multi-tenant network (if the use case requires ISP topological information). This agent is responsible for generating the topological information for all the devices, ports and connections between ports and devices available in the machine. To achieve this purpose, RIA is responsible for discovering the following information: i) Physical Machine and its logical and virtual network interfaces, ii) VMs and their virtual network interfaces, iii) Containers and their network interfaces, iv) Software switches, v) Specialised Physical Devices such as Software-Defined Radio (SDR) and their network interfaces, vi) Interconnection between network interfaces, and vii) Multi-tenant information of VMs. It is noted that the responsibility of v) is to overcome the challenge X depicted in Table 2.

Similarly, RIA can also be deployed inside the VMs of the 5G multi-tenant network (if the use case requires ISC topological information). When RIA is deployed only in physical machines (ISP domain), the VMs are considered as a black box where there is no information about what network topology is available inside such VMs. When RIA is deployed only in VMs (ISC domain), the topology reported is only the overlay network view for this particular tenant, and no information is revealed about the real ISP topology underneath. In a third case, when RIA is deployed in both ISP and ISC, both topological reports are combined in order to provide a complete topological overview. This is a significant innovation not achieved before, and the details of this joining process is described in Section 5. This is exactly the challenge XVI in Tables 1 and 2. The fulfilment of this new feature will allow overcoming challenge XVI by natural extension since once the alignment of data models is performed, the use case where ISP and ISC business roles are associated to the same business entity is supported.

Topology Inventory Manager (TIM) is a centralised component that provides information not available inside the computers/devices where RIA is deployed. This lack of availability could be for two different reasons. Firstly, RIA cannot be installed in closed hardware appliances and thus, in this cases,

topological information needs to be extracted out of the appliances from a centralised place. This is the reason why TIM is responsible for generating the topological information of all the hardware appliances where RIA cannot be installed, including managed switches and routers. Secondly, there are some cases where information is stored in the management software and not distributed to computers. These are architectural decisions of the management stack used and thus implementation-dependant. Therefore, in the cases where RIA cannot access such information, TIM will extract the information by its integration with the management stack. For example, in the case of OpenStack, the tenant information about the networks is only made available through management interfaces and never distributed into the computer nodes. The details of this integration will be explained in Section 5.

5G Mobile Agent (MA) is a centralised component that is deployed in each of the tenant networks that need to provide topological information about the UE and their mobility across different cells of the radio access networks. Monitoring topological information of UE across the different access points enables new capabilities related to the detection of deny of service attacks as proposed by Al-Dulaimi et al. [18]. To achieve so, this component is directly integrated with the Mobility Management Entity (MME) for the case of 4G architectures and with both SMF and AMF for the case of 5G architectures. SMF and AMF already track the UE to allow connectivity to them so that this 5G-MA just extracts such information to publish it in the “Topology” topic. This architectural component allows overcoming challenges XI and XII available in Tables 1 and 2.

Apart from these three topology agents, the proposed 5GTopoNet architecture has three more architectural components for management purposes as described below:

Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA) is the component that helps the spatial positioning of the topology reported by the different topology agents. LMA receives all the information about topologies being reported and runs customised algorithms to determine the best spatial allocation of all these components with

the main intention to provide useful and effective rendering of large-scale information to the network administrators. As a result of the layout algorithms, it publishes metrics indicating the spatial locations, which are later on used by other 5GTopoNet components to render the devices, ports and connection in the best possible locations for human understanding.

Graphical User Interface (GUI) renders the topology to the network administrators in order to facilitate troubleshooting. Fig. 2 shows how the same architectural component is divided into two different configurations. In one configuration, the user of this graphical component is the ISP, which implies that it can see every device, port and connection available in the topology. If ISC RIAs are instantiated, this mode allows seeing as well the topology of each of the tenants in a white-box approach. In the other configuration, the user is the ISC, and only the topology associated to that particular ISC is shown. An important filtering mechanism has been implemented in this component to make sure it does not receive unnecessary information to avoid privacy leakage.

Topology Persistor (TP) achieves the persistence of the topology information into a database, following a data lake approach where all the information is stored in a common place.

5. Design and Implementation

5.1. Design Approach

Fig. 3 depicts the architectural design of all the software components in 5GTopoNet. All the components for extracting the topology information (RIA, TIM and 5G-MA) have a similar design based on a plug-in based architecture that provides an extensible mechanism to on-board new capabilities to the architecture. They periodically extract the topological information from the managed system and keep it in an in-memory database that tracks the topological changes. Such changes are also reported periodically. Topology information is simultaneously received by TP, LMA and GUI. TP keeps an updated representation of the network topology in the database whereas GUI performs the

Figure 3: 5GTopoNet Architecture Design

rendering of such topology for the final users. To do such rendering, every device part of the topology needs to have associated their spatial coordinates. The coordinates are provided periodically by LMA by executing the algorithms implemented in the *GraphManager*. This layout algorithm is our customised version of Hu’s algorithm [19].

5.2. Data Model

Let us introduce the general principles of the 5GTopoNet data model used to describe the topological information. There are three key concepts in the data model: *Device*, *DevicePort* and *Connection*. A *Device* is any of the physical or logical devices in the infrastructure. It is described by means of a set of attributes such as a *deviceType*, a *model* or a *managementIPAddress*, among others. Among these attributes a subset is used to identify uniquely such a device. They are i) *HostName*, and ii) *tenantId* referring to the owner of the device (if any). A *DevicePort* is any network port in a *Device*. It has several attributes such as *macAddress*, *ipv4Address*, *ipv4Mask*, among others. Among these attributes, a subset is used to identify uniquely such a port. They are i) *interfaceName*, ii) *HostName* and iii) *tenantId*. A *Connection* is mainly composed by a *srcResource* and a *dstResource* and represents connections between

330 *Devices* or between *DevicePorts*.

5.3. ISP and ISC Data Model Alignment

5.3.1. Physical and Virtual Host Alignment

The challenge is to achieve that the reporting of the *Devices* and *DevicePorts* for VMs/containers is exactly the same for those attributes that identify uniquely such resources, thereby allowing the alignment of data models.

To do so, 5GTopoNet leverages the usage of a new functionality in recent Linux kernels coined as *Predictable Network Interface Names*. This feature has been included in v197 of the systemd/udev kernel module, and it is activated by default onward. The original reason why this feature has been included in the kernel is that classic naming scheme for network interfaces makes the assignment of the interfaces' names not deterministic. Thus, classic naming assigns names in order ("eth0", "eth1", ...) to all interfaces as they are probed by the drivers. However, the driver probing is generally not predictable for modern technology, which makes the naming not deterministic as soon as multiple network interfaces are available.

This new feature incorporates the name of the network interface and the type of interface, e.g. on motherboard interfaces (eno1) and PCI Express (ens1). The name also includes the PCI slot ID or the index number of the interface for on-board devices. Thus, for example, the interface enp2s1 refers to the PCI Express network card connected to the second PCI slot and within the network card, refers to the first port available in the card.

Thus, when RIA is installed in the physical machine, it has access to the inventory of VMs/containers created inside this machine. The inventory contains the description of such machines, including memory size, hard disk and network interfaces. The description of such network interfaces includes to which virtual bus ID they are connected, and to which virtual port in such virtual network cards they are connected. This information is retrieved from RIA, and it is able to "predict" the name that the interface will have inside the operating system of this machine. The "prediction" of the *hostName* of such a VM will

360 correspond to the name of the VM in the management stack. The manage-
ment stack injects such a name when the VMs are created using the cloud-init
mechanisms ¹ so that they can be “predicted” as well. Finally, the information
about the owner/tenant of such a VM is directly available in the host machine.
Thus, for example, a virtual network interface of a given VM that is connected
365 to Bus 3 and port 1 will be predicted as *enp3s1*. The reported information
about such interfaces would be *DevicePort=enp3s1; HostName=AMF; tenan-
tId=24423-52341-35287-32345*.

When RIA is installed inside the VM of a given tenant, it receives the ID of
the tenant it belongs to as a configuration parameter. Thus, when extracting
370 the topological information, it uses such configuration parameters as *tenantId*,
and both hostname and network interface name will match those predicted by
the RIA running in the physical machine.

5.3.2. 5G Distributed Unit Alignment

The challenge is to achieve that the reporting of the *Distributed Units* (DUs)
375 for VMs to be exactly the same for those attributes that identify uniquely such
resources, thereby allowing the alignment of data models. Two different types
of DUs have been investigated. On the one hand, there are some 5G DUs that
are connected using an Ethernet interface. In this first case, the strategy is
to follow exactly the same approach indicated in the alignment between vir-
380 tual and physical machines. On the other hand, there are 5G DUs that are
connected to the physical machine using a USB interface. In this second case,
the USB is connoted directly to the VM/containers using a USB pass-through
technology. The key approach used to align data models employs the USB se-
rial number and USB PCI address that are a unique identifier of the DU and
385 its communication interface, respectively. Both are accessible from both VMs
and physical machines. Moreover, the USB pass-through is initiated by the
management plane of the physical machine. Thus, the RIA can know what

¹Cloud-init is available at <https://cloud-init.io/>

tenantId is the target VM being passed through and in consequence, is able to report information about such interfaces as *DevicePort=2500:0200; Host-*
390 *Name=070001874500; tenantId=24423-54341-35287-32345*. Analogously, when the RIA is installed inside the VM of a given tenant, values will match those extracted by the RIA running in the physical machine.

5.3.3. Aligned Data Models

As a result, both data models are aligned to allow a dual view of ISP and
395 ISC topologies and also allow the support of the corresponding use cases. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to align data models belonging to different 5G business roles under the same common umbrella. Moreover, there are several implications to this alignment. One is the first definition of the security and privacy boundaries between business roles. The information
400 exposed between them is equivalent in the physical world to allow one's customer to enter one's premises to see the chassis of a computer but not allow the customer to interact with this computer. It is noted that to see the chassis allows someone to infer a lot of information, including the number of physical devices connected, if it is powered on or off, how many PCI slots it has and what
405 PCI slots are the cards connect to, among others. This is analogous to what it means in the virtualisation/containerisation world when using our enabling approach.

5.4. Implementation Details

In terms of implementation, all the components have been implemented
410 in Java 8, and they are executed in computers running Linux with the only exception of the GUI which has been implemented in .Net C# and running in Windows. TIM has been integrated with SNMP devices with support for both LLDP and CDP discovery protocols and also with OpenStack Queens² to extract multi-tenant information. RIA has been integrated with Linux namespaces/containers (ip netns) , Linux Hardware inventory tools (lshw and lspci),
415

²OpenStack Queens is available at <https://www.openstack.org/software/queens/>

software switches (Open vSwitch and Linux Bridges) and LLDP/CDP Discovery tools (lldpcli). 5G-MA has been integrated with both Mosaic5G Stack (development branch) ³ and also NextEPC (development branch) ⁴. In both cases, 5G-MA extracts the topological information in the following way. 5G-
420 MA is integrated with MME and PGW in the Core Network for pre-5G core implementations and will be integrated with SMF and AMF when 5G native core networks are available. The integration with MME allows extracting the relationship between the International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) and DU id. The integration with the Packet Data Network Gateway (PGW) al-
425 lows extracting the IP address of the UE associated to the IMSI. With the DU id, the 5G-MA knows which DU the UE is connected to. This information allows continuously tracking UE along the network. TP has been integrated with MySQL 5.5 ⁵ as a persistence back-end. This integration has been carried out to validate all the functionalities claimed, and the plugin-based approach makes
430 the architecture extensible, and thus further functionalities can be added later on. GUI has been integrated with Unity 2018.1 ⁶. The integration of TIM to OpenStack was especially challenging, and it is worth mentioning the approach. Fig. 3 shows a simplified OpenStack architecture where both Nova and Neutron components are publishing to different topics the internal information of
435 OpenStack, and at the same time this is stored in a database. Our integration has been hooked in both OpenStack database and also message bus in order to allow a rapid near real-time response in topological changes.

5.5. Workflow of the Framework

To provide a better understanding about the interaction between all the
440 architectural components of the proposed framework, a sequence diagram is provided in Fig. 4. RIA, TIM, 5G-MA, LMA and GUI are the software com-

³Mosaic5G is available at <http://mosaic-5g.io/>

⁴NextEPC is available at <https://nextepc.org>

⁵MySQL is available at <https://www.mysql.com/>

⁶Unity is available at <https://unity.com/>

Figure 4: 5GTopoNet framework sequence diagram

ponents that compose the framework and they interact with each other using two message exchanges by employing a message broker middle-ware system: topology exchange and metrics exchange.

445 The operation of the framework can be reduced to four loops. The first one represents a RIA software instance (as example of all the distributed RIA instances deployed in the system). It reports periodically changes in the topology of the machines they are installed. Similarly, TIM and 5G-MA gather their corresponding topological information at the same periodic interval. These actions
 450 are repeated every x seconds to keep the information updated, but it does not mean that the three agents have to do it in the same time interval. These components send the topological information discovered to the (*Topology Exchange*) where LMA and GUI are subscribed and therefore they receive such topological information.

455 The fourth loop represents a different procedure. After LMA receives a change in the topology, it generates a topology structure. This structure is reported to *Metrics Exchange* where the GUI is subscribed. Then, the GUI will update the topology structure rendering the topology components with respect to the new

spatial positions.

460 **6. Empirical Results**

This section describes a set of validation and scalability tests that have been conducted over the 5GTopoNet architecture in order to prove the claimed contributions with the level of scalability achieved.

6.1. Testbed Description

465 The validation tests in this work have been performed in a real 5G multi-tenant infrastructure testbed. This infrastructure is composed of one computer in the Core network, and one computer in each of the two Edge networks. Each of these computers is a high-performance laptop EUROCOM Sky X9E3, with Intel CPU i7 7700K 4.2GHz and 64GB RAM DDR4-2400. In both Edges, there
470 are two USRP B210 SDR DUs to connect 5G mobile phones. Each SDR DU has an antenna operating at Band7 with a duplexer. The core and edges are connected through a switch that allows a complete data path. The management computer where the 5GTopoNet architecture has been deployed is a Dell T5810, with Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 2.20GHz, 32GB RAM, and 512GB SDD.
475 It runs a Windows 10 platform where TIM, TP, LMA, 5G-MA and GUI are installed. RIA is deployed in each of the computers of the infrastructure.

6.2. 5G Multi-tenant Infrastructure Validation

The infrastructure is managed by OpenStack ⁷, a well-known cloud stack platform. Two different tenants of the infrastructure are deployed. Each of the
480 tenants has a set of VMs in the Core network and one container in each of the Edges. KVM ⁸ and LXC ⁹ have been used for this purpose. Each tenant runs Mosaic5G ¹⁰ as the 5G radio access platform to allow the UE devices to access

⁷OpenStack is available at <https://www.openstack.org/>

⁸KVM is available at <https://www.linux-kvm.org>

⁹LXC is available at <https://linuxcontainers.org>

¹⁰Mosaic5G is available at <http://mosaic-5g.io/>

Figure 5: 5GTopoNet ISP screenshot of our 5G MEC Infrastructure

Figure 6: 5GTopoNet ISP screenshot of an Edge physical machine opened to unveil the complexity of the software data path available inside

the network. To be concrete, the CU runs in the containers at the Edges, and
 the whole EPC runs inside of the same machine in the Core network for simpli-
 485 fication. NextEPC has been employed as the Core network since Mosaic5G has
 not provided support for UE handover across antennas. Both are supported by
 5G-MA by their integration with the MME and SGW/PGW software compo-
 nents. The modular architecture of the 5G-MA will allow extensible support
 for native implementations of 5G Core networks when available. The SDR has
 490 been configured to use 2x2 MIMO and to broadcast the network, via Public
 Land Mobile Network (PLMN) broadcast, for the tenant network it belongs to.

Fig. 5 shows a screenshot of the result of the discovery of the 5G topology using 5GTopoNet. As shown, there are two different Edges where two different SDR DUs are connected to each of the Edge. Then, eighth different UE devices are discovered to be currently connected to the network. The Edges are located on
495 different floors, and the two SDR DUs are allocated on the same floor whilst belonging to different tenants. This is why the balance in the number of UE devices connected to each SDR can be controlled. The Edge physical machines host two different containers (running the CU software). They are depicted in
500 different colours to represent the tenant information. The two Core computers are used to get access to the external servers (two connected to each Core network) through a switch. The Core computers run two VMs, one per tenant with the EPC software. There is a fifth physical machine close to the centre of the network, which is the OpenStack Neutron machine used to get access to the
505 Internet. This machine also hosts two different containers used by Neutron to provide DHCP services for each of the tenant networks. The figure shows the complexity associated to the software data path by making using of a tailored 3D spatial disposition of the components. Moreover, when the user clicks on any of the machines, it is opened in order to show the complex data path available
510 inside of it. Fig. 6 shows the discovered information about such a data path. It is worth mentioning how a software switch is depicted in the figure connecting the different VMs with the physical machine and its physical network interfaces. This is an Open vSwitch software employed to perform tenant isolation, to control security policies and to allow communications between the VMs belonging
515 to the same tenant. A user can see logical "tun/tap" interfaces, physical interfaces, interconnections with the Linux kernel in a very simple way, even with the incredible complexity associated with the discovery of these configurations.

The visual distribution of the devices has been tackled by LMA to maximise the visibility understandably. The figure shows how both 5G users and
520 multi-tenancy are visualised. When a user is experiencing a handover across antennas, it is animated in the GUI. Thus, this section has validated the three first innovations claimed in Section 1.

6.3. Validation of Business Role Separation

Figure 7: 5GTopoNet screenshot of the ISC view

Fig. 5 described in Section 6.2 represents the case where the ISP can see
525 the complete overview of the infrastructure. When the ISP clicks on a physical
machine, it is able to see the content of the machine since it is the owner,
as depicted in Fig. 6. However, when the ISP clicks on a VM, it will see
either an empty box with no further information or the complete rendering of
the software data path, similar to the one depicted for the physical machine,
530 depending on if the ISP also has an ISC role (ISP + ISC scenario) or not. The
scenario running in our infrastructure is an ISP + ISC scenario where both
RIAs report information to validate the alignment of data models. Both figures
of the software data path of a VM has been included as sub-figures in Fig. 8.
It is noted that the links from the physical machines depicted in Fig. 5 exactly
535 match the link interfaces of the VMs shown in Fig. 8, and this has validated
the alignment of interfaces between physical and virtual machines described in
Section 5.3.3.

Another scenario is that when a given tenant (ISC) is logged in the 5GTopoNet GUI, it can only have access to the information related to its virtual
540 network, and all the information related to other tenants or to the physical machines will be hidden. Fig. 7 displays the information shown to ISC - Tenant

Figure 8: 5GTopoNet screenshot of the software data for VMs on different business roles

A. It is noted that it matches all the red boxes depicted in Fig. 5, although now the tenant is not able to have any information about the location of their VMs with respect to the physical machines or how many physical machines are available, and so on. Probably, the most significant change of this view is related to the fact that now the DU is connected directly to the VM/container rather than to the physical machine (see A). Such a connection represents the USB pass-through described in Section 5.3.2. An ISC is only able to see the DUs and 5G UE devices under its control. It is noted that this section has validated the last three innovations claimed in Section 1.

6.4. Overhead and Performance Analysis

The purpose of this subsection is to provide an analysis of performance and overhead of each software component available in the proposed framework. The components in charge of reporting topological information are RIA, TIM and 5G-MA. Regarding TIM and 5G-MA, they are deployed in specific management machines due to their centralised nature and they are integrated with the control plane of the network, leading to an almost no consumption of resources and to no scalability concerns. However, RIA needs to be installed in every physical and virtual machine (depending the business role). This means that this is crucial for scalability and its computational cost need to be analysed.

Fig. 9 provides two graphs, aligned in time, plotting RIA behaviour along

Figure 9: RIA computational load while discovering all the resources of a compute server

two minutes of execution. This RIA instance was running in the core network described in the *Testbed Description* and responsible for discovering only the devices of such machines. RIA was reporting 115 devices being discovered. Graph 9a shows the percentage of CPU consumed. It is noted that after 30 seconds the component reached a steady state and the percentage of CPU was less than 3%. Graph 9b shows the memory usage in the same period of time. In this case, the amount of memory for stabilisation in approximately 5 seconds was around 80 MiB. This is the real footprint in terms of control overhead.

Figure 10: Communication load when discovering a whole topology

To represent the communication load in the system, Fig. 10 shows the band-

width usage required when discovering the largest topology scenario analysed in this manuscripts (35000 devices). Each peak of the graph is approximately 290 Kbps and it happened at regular intervals, which matched the refresh rate of all the discovery components (TIM, RIA, 5G-MA). In the bootstrapping process (the first 15 seconds of execution), there was one peak of exactly 2.27 Mbps where the whole topology was being discovered for the first time and then it was updated at regular intervals.

Figure 11: 5GTopoNet GUI computational load from starting until stabilisation after render the whole topology

Finally, Fig. 11 provides two graphs, aligned in time, depicting the computational load of the GUI. These results have been taken again for the largest scenario analysed. Graph 11a shows the percentage of CPU used in the machine where the GUI is deployed. After rendering the topology, the GUI stabilised at around 20% of CPU usage. Graph 11b shows the total amount of memory used along the whole process of receiving and render the topology. The memory stabilised at around 670 MiB when the topology has been rendered. This is a clear demonstration of the scalability of the proposed architecture.

There are two important moments in the graphs plotted in Fig. 11. The first one is at the beginning, where the GUI was receiving the topological information and the second one is at second 115 approximately where the GUI started receiving the information from LMA about the layout positions and when the GUI started rendering the topology.

6.5. Scalability Results

This section performs a scalability test of the 5GTopoNet architecture to analyse how much complexity in the topologies can be handled by the proposed approach. To this end, an emulator of the JSON interface reported by *RIA*, *TIM* and *MA* has been created to be able to scale up the managed infrastructure far beyond the current infrastructure available in our premises. It has been used to emulate the behaviour of a significant number of RIA components as if they were deployed in each of the emulated physical and virtual machines of the topology to analyse how the architecture behaves under stressed conditions.

Property	Min value	Max value	Function
Number of <i>UE</i> x <i>DU</i>	1	64	$\sum_{i=0}^6 2^i$
Number of <i>DU</i> x <i>Edge</i>	2	2	<i>CONST</i> (2)
Number of <i>Tenants</i> x <i>Edge</i>	4	4	<i>CONST</i> (4)
Number of <i>Edge</i>	1	256	$\sum_{i=0}^8 2^i$
Number of <i>Servers</i> x <i>Tenant</i>	1	1	<i>CONST</i> (1)
Number of <i>Tenants</i> x <i>Core</i>	4	4	<i>CONST</i> (4)
Number of <i>Core</i>	1	64	$\sum_{i=1}^6 2^i$

Table 3: Ranging of generated scenarios for empirical validation experiments

Table 3 shows how the complexity of the topology was ranged, using an exponential incremental step in complexity and a fixed value respectively. The tests ranged the number of UE devices connected to each DU, the number of Edge locations and the number of computers available in the Core network, since these are the key aspects of a 5G MEC infrastructure, thereby allowing a realistic analysis of the usability in these scenarios. The number of tenants, DUs available in each of the Edge locations, the number of servers in each of the Edge and the number of servers connected to each of the Core computers were fixed for simplicity. Scenarios were ranged up to 37,328 ($256 + 256 * 4 + 256 * 2 + 256 * 2 * 64$) + ($64 + 64 * 4 + 64 * 4 * 1$) + (3344 from other devices)

610 devices and 74,656 connections (two connections per device in average), for the most complex scenario analysed, constituting a very realistic topological size for a small city scale.

Figure 12: Sequence diagram of the experiment setup

Fig. 12 depicts a sequence diagram of the scalability results to understand how times were gathered. Experiment Controller is a script that started all the components from a cool start, and the topology information (JSON) was sent in chunks at regular intervals (1 sec). Then LMA and GUI received such information. LMA then recalculated the layout on every reception and when the layout was calculated, it sent the coordinates to the GUI. When the GUI had both coordinates and topological information, the end user e.g., an administrator would be allowed an interactive navigation along the virtual world for troubleshooting and other purposes.

Fig. 13 shows how 5GTopoNet behaved when the complexity of the topology to be discovered was exponentially growing in terms of both the number of UE devices and the number of Edges. The scenario depicted had 64 computers in the Core network. The time shown was the time from the arrival of the first JSON file from the RIA (emulator) until the latest device was rendered in the GUI. This is a black-box analysis where the interaction between all the components is not analysed, whilst only the final user perception was taken into consideration. To be precise, the time interval was from the first (3.1) step to

Figure 13: 5GTopoNet performance GUI-completed drawn time for each scenario

630 the last (3.3) step in Fig. 12. Fig. 13 plots two different series related to the analysis of the two different business roles: ISP and ISC. For the ISP, as shown, for up to 128 Edges running 32 UE devices or up to 32 Edges running 128 UE devices. 5GTopoNet provided very reasonable results of around 300 seconds, i.e., 5 minutes to converge a network composed by more than 6,992 devices and 13,984 connections to be discovered, positioned in space and rendered. In all the cases, more than 25 frames per second (FPS) were achieved. The same scenarios executed for the ISC provided better performance results of 216 seconds, due to the fact that fewer devices were rendered in the topology, to be precise, 1,477 devices and 2,954 connections. For the most complex scenario analysed, it went out of the scale and thus was plotted in the sub-figure depicted in Fig. 13. This scenario, for the ISP, took 100 minutes to discover and render 37,328 devices with 74,656 connections among them. The same scenario, for the ISC, took 81 minutes to discover and render 8,966 devices with 17,932 connections among them. After this initial discovery, the GUI resulted in 4-5 FPS in both business roles, too slow and impracticable to navigate the topology.

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Fig. 14 follows a black-box analysis of the LMA component to understand how much LMA contributed to the total times shown in Fig. 13. Fig. 14 shows

Figure 14: 5GTopoNet performance LMA- metrics generation time for each scenario

a very similar trend with respect to the behaviour of the whole architecture. It is noted that the LMA algorithm is non-deterministic. A total of 10 different executions were conducted. The best and the worst executions were removed to avoid outliers. These results correspond to the averages of the other eight executions. It is worth mentioning that the shapes of both Fig. 14 and 13 are similar but the time scales are completely different. The acceptable response times was around 100 seconds from the scenarios previously analysed. In the case of the most complex scenario, 328 seconds were required to position the devices and connections in the space. This was the time required to process the spatial layout of the complete infrastructure being discovered.

In order to better understand the limits of the scalability of 5GTopoNet, further tests were executed for the largest topology scenario with 128 UE devices, 256 Edges and 64 Cores (37,328 devices with 74,656 connections). Then, a white-box approach was taken for the understanding of the behaviour of the GUI, which is the component that contributes more to the time required to deal with the scalability of the system. To this end, Fig. 15 shows, at 5-second intervals, how many elements the GUI was able to draw at each interval for this scenario. It is noted that this representation allows measuring the per-

Figure 15: 5GTopoNet performance GUI- the number of elements drawn for each interval of 5 seconds

formance of the GUI along the time when the level of stress was progressively increased. The figure shows how the performance of the system was dropping with the number of rendered objects in the screen was increased. This dropping arrived to an inflexion point (see A) in Fig. 15 where the degraded performance was then maintained regardless of the size and complexity of the number of objects being rendered on screen. This point A in Fig. 15 represents the case where there were around 60 devices every 5 seconds, and thus at 1,800 seconds, there were around 35,000 devices with their respective connections. This is the scalability boundary of the proposed architecture.

In order to allow understanding the complexity and the shape of the topologies being discovered and rendered in 5GTopoNet, Fig. 16 shows a screenshot of one of the mid-sized topologies executed in the previous scalability tests. It displays a scenario featured with 512 UE devices connected to 32 different DUs that were located in 16 different Edges, 64 different computers allocated in the Core network, and 64 servers deployed to cross different administrative domains. As shown in the figure, the complexity is far beyond the understanding of a human being. Therefore, key tools to navigate that complexity and aid

Figure 16: 5GTopoNet GUI screenshot of a topology with 16 UE devices per Edge, 16 Edges and 16 Cores

administrators to fulfil their tasks are critical for the reduction in both capital and operating costs associated with network administration. This scenario is
 685 composed of 2,576 devices and 5,152 connections among them, and it took 67 seconds to discover and render this highly complex topology.

7. Conclusions

A novel architecture for the discovery of network topologies suitable for the novel 5G multi-tenant MEC architecture has been presented and validated. The
 690 architecture provides significant innovation beyond the state of the art, by allowing discovering not only physical infrastructures but also logical infrastructures that cannot be seen by humans directly for troubleshooting and other network management tasks. It provides a suitable alignment of the data models of ISP and ISC, enabling an enhanced level of flexibility by providing support to the
 695 vast majority of business models available in this kind of infrastructures. The prototype has been validated over a real 5G multi-tenant MEC infrastructure where complex physical and virtual data paths were discovered and rendered,

and users were enabled to navigate them to perform troubleshooting. The architecture has been proven to work with up to 37k devices, discovered and displayed
700 in 5 minutes when everything runs in a simple desktop computer. This is the level of scalability required for a small city scale, and thus the scalability performance is advantageous. The benefits achieved by using the 3D space to deal with the complexity of the topology has been significant, allowing end-users to understand, at a glance, where a VM is located, what tenant it belongs to, how
705 a 5G user is moving across antennas, what is the concrete data path available in the infrastructure and so on.

For future work, it is planned to provide metrics on each device and interface. It is also planned to include real-time flow monitoring. It will transform the current framework into a large-scale 3D monitoring tool. Moreover, to improve the scalability, by dealing with the group of devices together, with the
710 ambition to achieve more than 10 millions of devices discovered, monitored and rendered on the screen and users being able to understand these levels of complexity. Finally, it is also planned to use the tool as a debugger of the autonomic actions that are conducted by a cognitive pipeline where the management of the
715 infrastructure is performed without any human intervention.

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